

STUDYING SEASONALITY IN FOOD INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Introduction

Food security, and therefore food industry, is of a paramount importance in not only Uzbekistan, but also the whole world. The second goal of UN Sustainable Development Goals is shortnamed as “no hunger”, implying the need for food industry to be developed. In the Presidential decree of PF-4947 “About the Strategy of Actions in developing Uzbekistan further”, from February 7, 2017, food industry is set to be of leading directions for modernization and liberation. Seasonality in food industry is relevant to the issues of the general welfare of people, their utility from consumption, providing raw materials to other sectors, general employment levels and many others. This leads to the need for studying the seasonality patterns within an economy and try to analyse its impacts onto the whole economy.

On this ground, we take monthly dataset on food industry provided by the Ministry of Innovation, Industry and Trade of Uzbekistan and study the seasonality patterns in there together with their possible implications on the country’s economic stance and food security, suggesting policies to be implemented.

Analysis and results

Many researchers have taken up a study of seasonality in food markets. The list of facets seasonality plays role in economic phenomena is quite deep. For example, Feuerbacher *et.al.* (2020) have built a model for labour market incorporating the effects of seasonal changes in agricultural market. They applied their model in Bhutan economy and established that the government policies fail to accord with the seasonality feature of food markets, resulting in mistakes in assessing the employment, inflation volatilities, food security and household income. Miller and Malacarne (2023) develop multi-dimensional indicator for food accessibility in urban regions, applying it to data from the state of Maine, the US. They take availability, affordability and acceptability of food products as the basis for the new indicator and study the effects of farmer markets and traditional food retail changes on the total welfare of the society. Food seasonality appears in this context as the mediator of food security. They conclude that seasonality issue influences social welfare fluctuations negatively.

Similarly, Asefawu (2022) discusses the relationship between seasonal migration and household food security in the example of Ethiopia. Weather changes are found to negatively affect household welfare, food availability and access through long-term meteorological data analysis.

Another interesting aspect of seasonality analysis would be price fluctuations in the food industry. Kaminski *et.al.* (2016a) study 20 markets of Tanzania through 19 years. They estimate 27% increase in maize prices and 15% price increase in rice, which are the main crops in agriculture of many countries throughout the world. In another work, they conduct similar analysis 193 markets through Africa, assessing 33% and 16.5% price rises for maize and rice, respectively (Kaminski *et.al.*, 2016b).

One of the several important sidetracks on the topic would be the analysis of food storage availability. Brander *et.al.* (2020) conducts randomized control trials on Tanzanian food industry. They assess decreases of household food insecurities by 38% during the period between harvests and by 20% for the total year cycle. Similar results are accessed by Bohle and Adhikari (1998). They study international trade of Nepalese food industry and come to the conclusion that seasonality cause malnourishment and undernourishment because of storage inefficiency or insufficiency.

Studying the literature on food industry seasonality lays foundation for analysing Uzbek food market more efficiently. Conducting empiric studies into datasets with time series features, however, is claimed to be comparatively trickier process than cross-section. This is because it requires the analysis of variable dynamics, incorporating trend and seasonality (Gujarati and Porter, 2009).

The monthly dataset on food industry provided by the Ministry of Innovation, Industry and Trade of Uzbekistan contains data on food industry net product for 36 months from the start of 2021 to the finish of 2023. Figure-1 presents the line graph of the data obtained for analysis in logsrithmic values. According to the plot, it is fair to claim that the policies conducted by the government of the country has led for stable growth of the industry. A considerable downfall is observed for early 2022, signifying political distress in the world affecting economies. Nonetheless, constant fluctuations are observed through the time series, standing for seasonality patterns. These patterns should be divided into seasonality and trend.

Figure-1.

To assess seasonality in the time series provided, the initial operation of removing trend from the data should be conducted. This removal is suggested to be conducted through taking first difference of the variable (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). After cancelling the trend effects from the time series, one of the possible ways of identifying seasonality patterns is to construct corrollelogram. The constructed corrollelogram is presented in Figure-2. According to the results, the seasonality in the dataset is divided into two steps of increases and falls sequencing over a month.

Figure-2.

To identify the issue of lags in the dataset, the partial autocorrelation plot should be constructed. The resulting graph is presented in Figure-3. The partial autocorrelation plots serve the purpose of demonstrating autocorrelation orders and directions. This is mainly studied to clarify the existence autocorrelation problems in econometric models. As one of the possible autocorrelation sources in models is the existence of lags in economic effects, the partial autocorrelation plot is constructed for the dataset discussed herein. Figure-3 presents strong negative autocorrelation up to the eleventh period. Based on the fact that the main direction of found autocorrelation is negative, it can be inferred that the food industry of Uzbekistan undergoes comparative decreases from lags in the industry.

From the discussions presented above, it must be concluded that the seasonality exists in the food industry of Uzbek economy, which fluctuates over month. It is obvious that these new findings should be incorporated into the development of new government policies related to the food industry of the country. Ways to mitigate the issues brought about by the seasonality patterns and to take advantage of its existence should be constructed and proposed.

Figure-3.

Conclusions and recommendations

Having studied the literature on seasonality patterns in food industries and ways to identify them, their impact on different economic aspects, as well as conducting statistic analysis of the food industry of Uzbekistan, the following recommendations are developed and proposed:

- to increase the research into the seasonality patterns of food industry by dividing the processes into subgroups and clarifying the patterns originating within the industry and resulting from agriculture;
- to investigate the interrelationship between food industry and the whole economy in the light of existing seasonality patterns;
- to develop new processual methods on using seasonality in foodindustry in favor of the economy;
- to develop new means of hedging against the risks originating from seasonality of food industry in terms of food security;
- to identify the impact of seasonality of food industry on inflationary tendencies and mitigating the negative impacts;
- to study the development of storage infrastructure as a means of overcoming food industry seasonality.

Further research is needed into the sphere to make more precise conclusion and elaborate more pragmatic policy recommendations.

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